

A new approach to spinning egg-tops physics

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Abstract

We present a new approach to understanding the ascent of an ellipsoidal egg-top—a homogeneous solid spheroid rotating about a vertical axis on a flat table—based on observations from typical kitchen experiments, which show that the egg-top primarily self-rights by rolling. By decomposing the ascent into two stages—a “frictional capture” stage and a “rolling” stage—we obtain exact solutions of the equations of motion that effectively capture the egg-top’s behavior in both the *frictionless model* and the *rotary friction model*. The ascent time is computed exactly for a representative initial rotation speed, showing negligible differences between the two models. Two initial rotational speed thresholds are predicted: one below which the egg-top does not rise, and another below which it fails to reach the upright position. These results are summarized in curves prepared for future experimental investigations.

I INTRODUCTION

A - Existing approaches to describing the ascent of egg-tops

Why does a hard-boiled egg, when spun rapidly on a table, rise to an upright position (*see ExperimentalEggMovie-1.mov*)? This phenomenon is a well-known kitchen trick that helps distinguish a hard-boiled egg—which rises—from a still-fresh egg—which does not. Such an organic egg is an example of an “egg-top,” that is, any ovoid object that, when spun horizontally on a table, spontaneously assumes an upright position. Understanding the rise of egg-tops is no easy task, which is why it has challenged physicists for over a century.

As shown in the famous 1909 book by British mathematician Harold Crabtree [1], interest in the unique behavior of rotating ellipsoidal solids dates back over a century. In this work, he briefly described the “totally different” behavior of two “Chinese eggs,” one filled with water and the other empty. He then discussed the similar behavior of an “unboiled egg” and a “hard-boiled egg,” noting that the latter “always rises toward its long axis.”

In the most recent study on the ascent of a rotating egg [2], the authors address the “problem of an axisymmetric body rotating on a horizontal table.” They describe the motion using two non-independent angular velocities, resulting in

a set of coupled differential equations that cannot be disentangled. To address this, they employ the Lie symmetry method to deduce an analytical solution in abstract form. They further assume a constant viscous-type frictional force, corresponding to the case of an oiled table.

In an earlier article [3], the author presents his own formulation of the equations of motion, attributing a crucial role to a set of linear friction forces. Although he does not attempt to solve the equations, he conducts an experimental study of the ascent of smooth, small aluminum spheroids spun at high rotational speeds on a table, allowing him to make notable empirical observations. In particular, he identifies a threshold angular speed required for the spheroid to initiate its ascent, as well as a second threshold for it to reach its maximum elevation.

In [6], the authors express the equations of motion in a rather abstract form and assume too a constant viscous frictional force.

B - The simplest approach existing to date

In [4], the egg's ascent is described in a study that is still regarded by many

Figure 1: In their description of the egg's ascent, the authors of [4] call Ω the intrinsic precession speed around the Z axis and n the "spin", that is, the rotation speed around the ellipsoid main axis z . Not shown, the axis y and Y coincide and extend from the (OXZ) plane toward us. R is the reaction to the weight at the contact point P , and $h(\theta)$, the height of center of mass O , plays a crucial role in their calculations.

as a breakthrough that solved the problem [5]. However, we argue that their

conclusions are not fully justified; we present their approach in detail before explaining why it was necessary to reapply their strategy in search of a more accurate solution. The authors describe the ascent of an ellipsoidal solid body, considering—like us—that this is a necessary first simplification. Using the notations given in Figure 1, they apply the fundamental equations of rigid body rotation, namely Euler’s equations:

$$\left[\frac{d\vec{\sigma}}{dt} \right]_{R_I} = \left[\frac{d\vec{\sigma}}{dt} \right]_{R'/R_I} + \vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I} \wedge \vec{\sigma}_{R'/R_I} = \Sigma(\vec{M}_e). \quad (1)$$

In (1), $R' = (0xyz)$ denotes a rotating frame within the frame of reference $R_I(t) = (OX(t)Y(t)Z(t))$, both centered at O (Figure 1). This requires careful explanation. First, it should be noted that $R_I(t)$ —labeled with an I for “intrinsic” because it is linked to the egg—is not truly “fixed.” It rotates around the Z -axis relative to the laboratory frame $R_L = R_I(0) = (OX(0)Y(0)Z(0))$ with a precession speed $\Omega_P(t)$, and relative to itself—i.e., to the position reached on the table by the plane OXZ —with an intrinsic precession speed $\Omega(t)$. As stated by the authors of [4], $R_I(t)$ is therefore “a rotating frame of reference.”

This implies that $R_I(t)$ is not an inertial frame relative to R_L . To clarify what this means, recall that, by definition, in an inertial frame of reference, an object is not subject to any apparent external force arising from the motion of the frame itself. Therefore, just as the laboratory frame R_L , located on Earth’s surface, is not an inertial frame with respect to a reference frame centered at Earth’s center with fixed axes (the Earth frame), the egg’s intrinsic frame R_I is not an inertial frame relative to R_L . In R_I , the egg experiences various external forces due to its motion relative to the table, that is to R_L .

How do we transform between R_L and R_I ? This task becomes easy if we observe that when the egg precesses at a constant rate, we have $\Omega_P = \Omega$. If the precession is not uniform, then the change in the angle swept by $R_I(t)$ between t and $t + dt$, namely $[\Omega_P(t + dt) - \Omega_P(t)]dt$, must be canceled by the change in the angle swept by $R_I(t)$ relative to itself, that is, $[\Omega(t + dt) - \Omega(t)]dt$. Otherwise, $\Omega(t + dt) - \Omega(t)$ and $\Omega_P(t + dt) - \Omega_P(t)$ would not transform $R_I(t)$ into the same frame $R_I(t + dt)$: the accelerations of $R_I(t)$ with respect to itself and with respect to R_L must cancel each other out. This implies that $d\Omega_P/dt = -d\Omega/dt$, which, taking into account that $\Omega_P(0) = \Omega(0)$, leads to:

$$\Omega_P(t) = 2\Omega(0) - \Omega(t). \quad (2)$$

We now see that, by choosing the rotating intrinsic frame $R_I(t)$ as the “fixed” frame, the authors of the study did not err, as this choice does not hinder their ability to describe the ascent. In fact, this is advantageous, because by limiting their calculation to $R_I(t)$, they effectively decouple the description of ascent—their only concern, as well as ours—from the complications associated with other aspects of motion, such as translation on the table, precession and spin in the laboratory. We intend to emulate this winning strategy.

Let us now consider how the authors of [4] approached the solution of (1) : we now clearly understand that R' rotates about the Y – axis with angular speed

$\dot{\theta}'$ ($\theta' = \pi/2 - \theta$) within the (not truly) “fixed” frame R_I ; $\Sigma(\vec{M}_e)$ represents the sum of the applied external torques in R_I ; \vec{R} represents the reaction force counteracting the egg’s weight; the vectors $\vec{\sigma}_{R'/R_I}$ and $\vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I}$ denote the angular momentum and angular velocity. To express them, the authors of [4] use $\vec{\Omega}$, the intrinsic precession speed around the vertical axis and \vec{n} , the rotation speed around the ellipsoid’s major axis, which they refer to as the “spin” (Figure 1). This choice implies that $\vec{\Omega}$ and \vec{n} are not independent— ie. not perpendicular. As a result, the system of three Euler equations cannot be decoupled. To remedy this, they concentrate on the differential equation for θ and attempt to solve it approximately, employing one approximation ($|\dot{\theta}| < \Omega^2$) whose impact on the validity of the description we find difficult to assess. After some back-and-forth between the exact and approximate equations of motion they have derived and their original forms, the main result is reached:

$$J\dot{\theta} = -Fh^2(\theta)^2, \quad (3)$$

where J is a constant known as the “Jellet constant”, $h(\theta)$ is defined by figure 1 and F is a sliding friction force – for instance a Coulomb’s force – acting in opposition to the linear movement of the contact point P on the table. Given the crucial role of F in (3), the idea took hold that the egg straightens due to some elevating effect of this frictional force. We dispute this counterintuitive notion: the egg’s ascent cannot result from any sort of “friction motor.” In fact, since the energy driving the egg’s ascent is kinetic, the rise in angular velocity must correlate with the physical quantity representing this energy—namely, $\Omega_- = \Omega(0)$, the egg’s initial angular velocity. Therefore, instead of (3), we expect a general law governing the egg’s ascent of the following form:

$$\dot{\theta}' = \Omega_- f(\theta'), \quad (4)$$

where $\theta' = \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta$ and the egg’s rotation speed $\Omega(\theta')$ is a function of θ' starting at the value Ω_- and ending at $\Omega_+ > \Omega_-$. The function $f(\theta')$ is a dimensionless function of θ' that incorporates the effects of geometry (the egg’s shape), dynamics, gravity, and friction.

C - A novel approach to the ascent of the rotating egg

In what follows, we present a new approach to the problem of the ascent of a rotating solid ellipsoid on a flat table, yielding a law of ascent of the form given in (4). We use the same strategy as the authors in [4], but grounded in two new key observations: 1/ the instantaneous axis of rotation in the “fixed” intrinsic frame of reference that rotates with the egg is straightforward to determine ; 2/ for initial rotation speeds of a few revolutions per second, as encountered in kitchen experiments, the solid spheroid primarily rolls during its upward motion, allowing friction to be neglected for most of the ascent.

At first glance, one might question whether the egg truly rolls, yet close observation quickly dispels any doubt. In fact, it is clearly visible in any slow-motion video of a solid ellipsoid straightening up, in which regularly spaced ellipses pass-

ing through both ends of the spheroid have been drawn (see *ExperimentalEggMovie-1.mov*) or occur naturally, as seen on certain pumpkins (see *ExperimentalEggMovie-2.mov*). If C , the point of contact with the table, were to slip, these ellipses would show only minimal movement throughout the sequence; however, we observe them rotating and rapidly replacing one another.

Moreover, a careful listener will clearly hear that, during most of the ascent and throughout the descent, the egg emits a sound reminiscent of coins rolling on their edge after being rotated vertically. This distinct sound is characteristic of a hard body rolling on a hard flat surface, indicating – proving in fact – that the egg is rolling nearly continuously as it ascends and descends.

From these observations, we conclude that an egg launched optimally, will roll during most of the ascent. As we will see, this allows us to determine the instantaneous axis of rotation in the "fixed" frame R_I .

II. DETERMINING THE INSTANTANEOUS ROTATION AXIS

A simple observation reveals the instantaneous axis of rotation of the egg-top

Figure 2: *a: The egg's instantaneous rotation axis connects the contact point C to the center of mass G . In the case where the rotating ovoid is an ellipsoid, the egg's instantaneous rotation axis also passes through the vertex S . As the egg rises, the rotation vector ω_{R'/R_I} has a component aligned with CG and another once perpendicular to the median plane of the body, which we have not shown. In other words, $\vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I} = [\vec{\omega}, \vec{\varphi}]$, where φ is the angle between the horizontal plane and the long axis of the egg. *b: An instantaneous axis of rotation off the axis CG is hypothesized. *b: An instantaneous axis of rotation off the axis CG is hypothesized.***

in R_I : as illustrated in Figure 2a, the instantaneous axis of rotation of an ellipsoid that (rolls and) rotates on a table, touching it at a single point C , can

only be a line belonging to all the successive planes that, at each instant, divide the ellipsoidal egg into two equal masses: ie. CG .

However, if not convinced by the latter observation, we can also determine the instantaneous axis of rotation algebraically. Let us choose a (rotating yet) "fixed" intrinsic frame of reference $R_I = (GXYZ)$ based on the median plane of the egg, and assume – as a work hypothesis – that $\vec{\omega}$, the component of the of rotation vector $\vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I}$ in the egg's median plane, lies off the CG axis, as shown in figure 2b. The angular velocity $\vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I}$ reads :

$$\vec{\omega}_{R'/R} = [\vec{\omega}, \dot{\varphi}] = [\dot{\theta}_X, \dot{\theta}_Y, \dot{\theta}_Z] = [\omega \cos \gamma', \omega \sin \gamma', \dot{\varphi}],$$

where γ' is the angle separating the axis X from the rotation vector $\vec{\omega}$, γ the angle separating the axis X from the axis CG and φ the angle separating the axis X from the major axis of the ellipsoidal body (not shown in figure 2b). With these notations, and if we note r_C the radius of C , and use $\vec{GC} = [X_C, Y_C, 0] = [-r_C \cos \gamma, -r_C \sin \gamma, 0]$, the instantaneous velocity of the point of the egg in contact with the table at C is written:

$$\vec{V}_C = [\dot{\theta}_Z Y_C, \dot{\theta}_X Y_C - \dot{\theta}_Y X_C, \dot{\theta}_X Y_C - \dot{\theta}_Y X_C] = [-\dot{\varphi} r_C \sin \gamma, -\dot{\varphi} r_C \cos \gamma, \omega r_C \sin(\gamma' - \gamma)].$$

Now it is time to note that :

$$\dot{\theta}_X Y_C - \dot{\theta}_Y X_C = (\text{rotation speed}) - (\text{translation speed}),$$

because rotation around X moves C by lifting it, while rotation around Y moves C on the table without lifting it (along a circle). However, we have:

$$\dot{\theta}_X Y_C - \dot{\theta}_Y X_C = \omega r_C \sin(\gamma' - \gamma),$$

meaning that if, at time t , the egg rolls sufficiently, it prevents sliding at the instantaneous contact point $C(t)$ by lifting it, thereby ensuring :

$$\dot{\theta}_X Y_C = \dot{\theta}_Y X_C \Rightarrow \dot{\theta}_X Y_C - \dot{\theta}_Y X_C = 0 \Rightarrow \gamma' = \gamma,$$

which aligns the axis of rotation with CG !

Given that energy dissipation during rolling is several orders of magnitude lower than that of sliding, and that bodies tend to move in a way that minimizes energy loss, the egg will start rolling as soon as physically possible—to avoid sliding and ensure $\gamma' = \gamma$. We now understand that there is a strong physical constraint—namely, the reduction of energy expenditure—such that the egg, if it can, will roll as soon as possible for the majority of its movement.

It is important to note, however, that this process can only initiate if and only if a sufficient friction enables rolling. This arises from the fact that, for rolling to occur, the micro-asperities of the table and egg surfaces must be able to resist sliding by interlocking, somewhat like gears with small teeth. We call this phenomenon "frictional capture." It cannot occur when the initial vertical rotation speed—denoted as ω_- —is very high, meaning that sliding in a horizontal position likely continues until friction has reduced the rotation speed enough for frictional capture to take place. When rolling finally begins, it at least partially cancels sliding and induces ascent, although some residual sliding at the

point of contact may still occur. This implies that when the ascent begins, a significant proportion of the kinetic energy has already been dissipated through rotary friction at the point of contact. Our observations suggest that this complex behaviour at high initial rotation speeds ω_- does not occur in the kitchen experiments we focus on.

This leads us to define what we mean by "kitchen experiment". By this term, we refer to the study of the ascent of an ellipsoid set in rotary motion by hand on a kitchen table, typically at rotational speeds of less than 5 revolutions per second. To clarify why we impose this criterion, let's imagine a very quick person setting an egg in motion: this would involve turning the egg around — in, say, 0.1 seconds at the quickest — by swiftly reversing the positions of the thumb and forefinger. The resulting initial angular speed would therefore be at most $\pi/0.1 = 10\pi$, or about 5 revolutions per second. Therefore, we can assume that in "kitchen experiments", the order of magnitude of ω_- , the egg's initial rotational speed, will be about 5 revolutions per second or less.

We therefore needed an experimental egg-top with an ellipsoidal shape reasonably close to that of biological eggs, capable of being launched at speeds of a few revolutions per second. We chose to use one of the dummy wooden eggs commonly placed in a hen's nest to encourage laying. It appears that in Europe these dummy eggs are generally oval-shaped, whereas similar objects used in the United States are ellipsoidal, which aligns with the geometry assumed in this study. The fake American eggs ordered online turned out to be very ellipsoidal and strong, in fact ideal for withstanding a series of tests. Our measurements yielded the following values for their major and minor axes:

$$a = 6 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m}, \quad b = 4.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m}. \quad (5)$$

In our calculations, the following geometric parameter:

$$\epsilon = \frac{b}{a} \leq 1, \quad (6)$$

will be of great use. For our dummy experimental egg $\epsilon = 4.5/6 = 0.75$.

III. DESCRIBING THE EGG-TOP'S MOTION

A-Notations and two key formulas

To describe the egg's ascent, we now establish some notations, shown in Figure 3. The moving reference frame is denoted by $R' = (Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)$, whereas the "fixed" reference frame is $R_I = (Gxyz)$. Beyond this, the most important notations are the angle φ between the horizontal and the ellipsoid's major axis; the angle ν between that axis and $\vec{\omega}$, and the component of the rotation vector in the egg's median plane; and their sum:

$$\gamma = \varphi + \nu. \quad (7)$$

$r_C(\nu)$, the instantaneous radius to the contact point C , will also play a crucial role in our calculations. The polar equation of an ellipse with major axis a and

Figure 3: *The following notations are used in this schematic representation of the system: the center of mass G , the contact point C , and the egg's vertex S ; the axes x, y of the fixed reference frame $R_I = (Gxyz)$; the axes x_φ, y_φ and z_φ (with z and z_φ being merged) define the reference frame $R' = (Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)$, which moves with the egg.; the angles φ and ν , which are crucial for our calculations; the notations for the weight \vec{P} and the reaction \vec{R} ; finally, the radial coordinate $r_C(\nu)$ of point C in the frame $R' = (Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)$ is also indicated.*

minor axis b , measured from its center, readily gives:

$$r_C(\nu) = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{b^2 \cos^2 \nu + a^2 \sin^2 \nu}} = \frac{a\epsilon}{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \nu + \sin^2 \nu}}. \quad (8)$$

Moreover, for the calculations to be presented below, it will also be essential to recognize the existence of a “geometric constraint” linking φ and ν . Indeed, at each instant, $y_C = -r_C(\nu) \sin \gamma$ in the reference frame $R_I = (Gxyz)$ must be minimal. At a fixed φ , this condition translates into $d[r_C(\nu) \sin \gamma]/d\nu = 0$, which, as shown in Appendix 2, leads to:

$$\tan \varphi \cdot \tan \nu = \epsilon^2. \quad (9)$$

B-Describing the egg's ascent in two stages

Before discussing the general evolution of the egg's motion, it is important to note that a perfectly ellipsoidal egg, placed exactly horizontally on a perfectly

flat plane, will theoretically never rise. The two halves of the egg—equal masses in perfect equilibrium—will continue to rotate around the vertical axis. In this idealized case, the ellipsoidal egg does not straighten up, but rotates until the rotational friction exerted by the tiny contact at point C completely dissipates its kinetic energy.

In a typical kitchen experiment with $\omega_- \leq 5$ revolutions/s, the ascent occurs in two stages: a brief frictional capture followed by a rolling phase that continues until the egg reaches the vertical position. We now describe them.

Stage 1 : frictional capture

The first stage—the frictional capture—begins when, for any reason, such as an accidental nudge, an imperfect launch, or surface asperities on the table, the instantaneous axis of rotation becomes slightly tilted from the vertical by an angle φ_m . As explained in the previous section, although rotary friction at the contact point C opposes rotation about this axis during the frictional capture, the combined effect of rapid rotation and the egg’s shape generally causes it to quickly begin rolling and rising.

In this work, we assume that under typical kitchen-experiment conditions, linear friction is negligible. Therefore, we consider only the resistive torque \vec{C} produced by rotary friction. We explain in Appendix 1 how we derived a simple expression for \vec{C} from Coulomb’s law:

$$C(\nu) = \frac{1}{3}\mu_d MgD(\nu), \quad (10)$$

where μ_d is the dynamic dry friction coefficient characterizing the egg–table contact, and $D(\nu)$ is the diameter of the contact cup—a quantity to be determined experimentally as a function of ν . Among other factors, the dependence of $D(\nu)$ on ν arises from the curvature of the egg’s profile.

Despite this, we believe that, by assuming \vec{C} to be constant, an effective first model of resistive rotary friction can be obtained by replacing $D(\nu)$ with a realistic mean value D . This means that one may assume a constant resisting rotary torque $C = |\vec{C}|$ given by :

$$C = \frac{1}{3}\mu_d MgD. \quad (11)$$

Naked-eye observations show that the time it takes for the egg to begin rolling varies depending on the launch conditions and the nature of the table surface. With sufficient friction—for example, with a sufficiently rough egg such as a biological one—the ascent appears easy and rapid, whereas on a slippery surface, such as smooth ice, it seems completely impossible.

The ascent of an egg, when laid horizontally on a table, thus depends on the launching conditions. However, for eggs reasonably similar to biological ones, optimal conditions likely exist that minimize the duration of the rotary-friction phase. This is suggested by repeated observations of the descent: during this reverse motion, the egg appears to roll continuously until it begins to rotate about a vertical axis while lying on its side. Likewise, when the egg straightens

up, the transition from rolling during ascent to rotation about a vertical axis in the upright position seems smooth. There is apparently no discontinuity at all, and the egg passes continuously from its rolling motion to its upright rotation. From this, we deduce that for experimental ellipsoids resembling biological eggs, it is reasonable to assume a relatively brief frictional capture under optimal launching conditions—that is, a very short initiation of the egg’s rolling due to contact with the table. We account for this brief frictional capture by introducing a cut-off angle φ_c , at which all rotary friction has ceased.

Stage 2 : Rolling

Once the solid spheroid begins to roll, it straightens up and transitions smoothly into vertical rotation. At this stage, it is not considered worthwhile to account for rolling friction, since it is a minor effect and the modeling of rotational friction in stage 1 remains both incomplete and untested.

However, once this has been achieved —perhaps with the help of an “egg launcher”— future studies could also examine rolling friction in detail. The numerical simulation presented in [7] would then be helpful, especially since its underlying physical reasoning was refined in [8].

Summarizing our two models

To clarify our approach, we now specify the two friction models used to describe the egg-top phenomenon: the *rotary friction model* and the *frictionless model*. By rotary friction, we mean that a frictional torque \vec{C} is present—given by $C = \frac{1}{3}\mu_d MgD$ as in (11)—whereas no torque is present in the frictionless model. Both models are therefore characterized by three phenomenological parameters: D , the diameter of the contact cup, to be chosen reasonably; φ_m , the tilt angle; and φ_c , the phenomenological cut-off marking the end of frictional capture. The following table summarizes the two models, allowing readers to have a clear view of the phenomenological and physical parameters.

Model	Stage 1 range	Stage 2 range	Resistive torques
Rotary friction model	$\varphi_m \leq \varphi \leq \varphi_c$	$\varphi_c \leq \varphi \leq \pi/2$	Stage 1: $\frac{1}{3}\mu_d MgD$, Stage 2: 0
Frictionless model	-	$\varphi_m \leq \varphi \leq \pi/2$	Stage 1: 0, Stage 2: 0

IV EGG-TOP’S EQUILIBRIUM AND EQUATIONS OF MOTION

A. The forces applied to the egg-top and its dynamic equilibrium

When analyzing the motion of a rotating rigid body in its own frame of reference, it is important to consider both forces and torques to describe the evolution of linear and angular momentum. While the forces determine the instantaneous dynamic equilibrium of the rotating solid spheroid, the torques govern its rota-

tional motion, which in turn influences the ascent of the center of mass G . To understand how the egg-top's dynamic equilibrium is established at each instant t , we need to apply Newton's second law at the center of gravity G in the egg's intrinsic frame R_I at time t , expressed as $M\vec{a} = M d\vec{v}/dt = \Sigma \vec{F}_e$, where \vec{v} is the velocity, \vec{a} is the acceleration, and \vec{F}_e represents an external force. Recall that neither the egg's intrinsic frame of reference, $R_I = (Gxyz)$, nor the rotating frame relative to it, $R' = (Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)$, is inertial with respect to the laboratory frame R_L . Therefore, the egg experiences, in R_I , various centripetal accelerations due to its rotational motion. Using the conventions provided in Figure 3 to apply Newton's second law at its center of gravity G , we arrive at:

$$Ma_x = M(\omega_y^2 + \omega_z^2)r_C \cos\gamma - F_s \quad (12)$$

$$Ma_y = M(\omega_x^2 + \omega_z^2)r_C \sin\gamma + R - Mg \quad (13)$$

$$Ma_z = F_d, \quad (14)$$

where:

$$\vec{\omega}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)/(Gxyz)} = [\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z] = [\pm\omega \cos\nu, \pm\omega \sin\nu, \pm\dot{\varphi}], \quad (15)$$

is the angular velocity vector of the moving frame $(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)$ with respect to the "fixed" frame $R_I = (Gxyz)$. The symbol \pm is used to indicate both possible rotational directions. \vec{F}_s is the static frictional force at point C , opposing translation along the x -axis in the outward direction. For completeness, we consider here a dynamic frictional force, \vec{F}_d , opposing translation along the z -axis, even though this force may not exist and is not included in our model. Since the spheroid is rigid, it transmits forces. Consequently, the weight $M\vec{g}$ acts at the contact point C , where it is balanced by the normal reaction force \vec{R} . Therefore, we have $R = Mg$.

(12) reflects the fact that rotation about the y -axis and z -axis generates two centripetal forces that act in opposition to the static frictional force F_s . According to Coulomb's law for static friction, we have $F_s = \mu_s R = \mu_s Mg$, where μ_s is the egg-table coefficient of static friction which varies in proportion to the centripetal force until it reaches a maximum, beyond which the egg begins to slide outwards. This happens rapidly if the table is slippery.

(13) reflects the fact that rotation about the x -axis and z -axis gives rise to two centripetal forces that tend to elevate the egg's center of mass G . While the torque of the weight plays a role in the motion, the force of the weight $M\vec{g}$ itself does not, as it is canceled out by the normal reaction force \vec{R} . Therefore, considering that $R = Mg$, equation (13) can be simplified to $a_y = dv_y/dt = (\omega_x^2 + \omega_z^2)r_C \sin\gamma$, which describes the ascent of G .

(14) illustrates that, contrary to what is stated in equation (3), the only effect of a (hypothetical) dynamic Coulomb friction force F_d would be to slow the egg's rotation about the z -axis. According to Coulomb's law for dynamic friction, we have $F_d = \mu_d R = \mu_d Mg$, where μ_d is the coefficient of dynamic friction between the egg and the table.

We observe that, while (13) describes the egg's ascent or descent, it cannot be

used without expressions for ω_x and ω_z . Thus, it is clear that solving the differential equations for angular momentum—specifically, Euler’s equations for rigid body dynamics given in (1)—is necessary to address the problem.

B. Writing Euler’s equations for rigid body dynamics

Using the notations of figure 3, we now want to translate Euler’s equations for rigid body dynamics, ie. equation (1), which, let us recall it, reads:

$$\left[\frac{d\vec{\sigma}}{dt} \right]_{R_I} = \left[\frac{d\vec{\sigma}}{dt} \right]_{R'/R_I} + \vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I} \wedge \vec{\sigma}_{R'/R_I} = \Sigma(\vec{M}_e).$$

In (1), $\vec{\sigma}_{R'/R_I}$ and $\vec{\omega}_{R'/R_I}$ represent the angular momentum and angular velocity of the egg in the frame $R' = (Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)$, which rotates with angular speeds ω and $\dot{\varphi}$ relative to the (rotating yet) "fixed" intrinsic frame of the egg, $R_I = (Gxyz)$. Additionally, $\Sigma(\vec{M}_e)$ represents the sum of the applied external torques, including the torque due to weight and the resistive frictional torque $\vec{C}(t)$. It is essential to note that in Figure 3, φ and ν are defined in the direct, ie. counterclockwise, direction. We emphasize that $0 < \varphi < \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\frac{\pi}{2} > \nu > 0$. In addition to these conventions, we note that the previously introduced angle $\gamma = \varphi + \nu$ varies between a minimum value and $\pi/2$. Indeed, when $\varphi = 0$, it starts at $\pi/2$ and returns to this value when $\varphi = \pi/2$.

We now need to give all the moments of inertia of an homogenous ellipsoid of mass $M = \rho \frac{4}{3} \pi ab^2$, ρ being its density. We simplify this by first giving the moment of inertia of an ellipsoid of revolution with respect to any axis x_ν , rotated by an angle ν relative to its principal axis x_φ :

$$J_\nu = \frac{Ma^2}{5} [2\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \nu + (1 + \epsilon^2) \sin^2 \nu] = \cos^2 \nu J_{x_\varphi} + \sin^2 \nu J_{y_\nu}, \quad (16)$$

from which we can readily deduce:

$$J_{x_\varphi} = \frac{Ma^2}{5} 2\epsilon^2, \quad (17)$$

$$J_{y_\varphi} = \frac{Ma^2}{5} (1 + \epsilon^2), \quad (18)$$

$$J_{z_\varphi} = \frac{Ma^2}{5} (1 + \epsilon^2). \quad (19)$$

For its part, the sum of the applied torques $\vec{M}(t) = \Sigma(\vec{M}_e)$ reads:

$$\vec{M}(t) = \vec{GC} \wedge \vec{R} + \vec{C}(\varphi) = [-C(\varphi) \cos \nu, -C(\varphi) \sin \nu, -Mg.r_C(\nu) \cos \gamma],$$

where we took into account that $|\vec{R}| = Mg$ and the fact that the angle between \vec{GC} and \vec{R} is $\pi - (\frac{\pi}{2} - \gamma) = \frac{\pi}{2} + \gamma$, so the sine of this angle is $-\cos \gamma$. (15) gives the angular velocity in the rotating frame R' , and we now present the angular momentum:

$$\vec{\sigma}_{R'/R_I} = [\pm J_{x_\varphi} \omega \cos \nu, \pm J_{y_\varphi} \omega \sin \nu, \pm J_{z_\varphi} \dot{\varphi}]. \quad (20)$$

In these expressions, the presence of \pm in front of each component reflects the fact that rotation can occur in either direction. Using all these expressions, we detail in Appendix 3 the straightforward derivation of the three coupled equations of motion:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}[\pm J_{x_\varphi} \omega \cos \nu] \pm (J_{z_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi}) \omega \dot{\varphi} \sin \nu &= -C(\varphi) \cos \nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[\pm J_{y_\varphi} \omega \sin \nu] \pm (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{z_\varphi}) \omega \dot{\varphi} \cos \nu &= -C(\varphi) \sin \nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[\pm J_{z_\varphi} \dot{\varphi}] + (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi}) \omega^2 \cos \nu \sin \nu &= -M g r_C(\nu) \cos \gamma.\end{aligned}$$

To fully understand these equations, it is essential to note that the signs on the two sides have different meanings: on the left-hand side, they indicate the direction of rotation, whereas on the right-hand side, they signify that the frictional torque is resistive. We can therefore multiply the left-hand side by \pm , while retaining the negative sign on the right-hand side, and write more simply:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}[J_{x_\varphi} \omega \cos \nu] + (J_{z_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi}) \omega \dot{\varphi} \sin \nu &= -C(\varphi) \cos \nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[J_{y_\varphi} \omega \sin \nu] + (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{z_\varphi}) \omega \dot{\varphi} \cos \nu &= -C(\varphi) \sin \nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[J_{z_\varphi} \dot{\varphi}] \pm (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi}) \omega^2 \cos \nu \sin \nu &= -M g r_C(\nu) \cos \gamma.\end{aligned}$$

C. Reduction from three to two equations of motion

We now notice that the second equation is nothing more than the first, in which we have replaced ν by $\nu + \frac{\pi}{2}$ and inverted J_{x_φ} and J_{y_φ} . This reflects the fact that while the first of these equations expresses what happens along the x_φ axis, the second expresses what happens along the y_φ axis. These two equations are therefore equivalent: each linked to its axis, they describe the same motion, so one or the other is sufficient, or any combination of the two. To keep the calculations as symmetrical as possible, we choose to multiply the first by $\cos \nu$ and the second by $\sin \nu$ and add them together, which we have detailed in Appendix 4. We come to the reduced system of equations of motion:

$$J_\nu \frac{d\omega}{dt} - (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi}) \omega \cos \nu \sin \nu (\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu}) = -C(\varphi), \quad (21)$$

$$J_{z_\varphi} \frac{d\dot{\varphi}}{dt} \pm (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi}) \omega^2 \cos \nu \sin \nu = -M g r_C(\nu) \cos \gamma. \quad (22)$$

Note that $J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi} = (1 - \epsilon^2) M a^2 / 5$, $\cos \nu \sin \nu$ and $\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu}$ are all three positive quantities, notably because $\dot{\nu} < 0$ (ν goes from $\frac{\pi}{2}$ to 0). This implies that when $d\omega$ and $d\varphi$ are positive (ascent), equation (21) describes an increase in ω , reduced by the work of a certain frictional torque; when $d\omega$ and $d\varphi$ are negative (descent), equation (21) remains unchanged, and to describe the descent, we simply need to choose $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ as the initial condition. The same applies to

equation (22), where we emphasize that the negative sign corresponds to an increase in $\dot{\varphi}$, ie. the egg's ascent, while the positive sign corresponds to a decrease in $\dot{\varphi}$, ie. the egg's descent.

VI. SOLVING THE EGG-TOP EQUATIONS OF MOTION

A. Quasi-exact solutions in the rotary friction model

Before presenting the explicit solutions for the frictionless model, we wish to point out that exact solutions of a model including rotary friction in the form of a constant resistive torque \vec{C} are within reach. We will not go into the technical details of transforming equations (21) and (22) here, as these are provided in Appendix 5. It suffices to note that, with the following definitions:

$$h(\varphi) = \epsilon^2 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi, \quad (23)$$

$$H(\varphi) = \epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi, \quad (24)$$

$$G(\varphi) = \epsilon^2(1 + \epsilon^2) \cos^2 \varphi + 2 \sin^2 \varphi, \quad (25)$$

the equations of motion for $\omega(\varphi)$ and for $\dot{\varphi}(\varphi)$ can be written as,

$$\frac{d\omega}{d\varphi} - (1 - \epsilon^4) \omega \frac{h(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)G(\varphi)} \cos \varphi \sin \varphi = - \frac{5}{Ma^2 \epsilon^2} \frac{H(\varphi)C(\varphi)}{G(\varphi)} \frac{1}{\dot{\varphi}}, \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}^2]}{d\varphi} = 2\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega^2 - 10 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}} \quad (27)$$

Now, suppose that we know the explicit solution $\omega_0(\varphi)$ of the homogeneous equation associated with (26), and that we also know $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$, the explicit solution of (27) obtained by substituting $\omega_0(\varphi)$ for $\omega(\varphi)$ in (27). Then, applying the method of variation of parameters and expanding $\dot{\varphi}(\varphi)$ in powers of C yields:

$$\omega(\varphi) = \omega_0(\varphi) \lambda(\varphi), \quad (28)$$

$$\lambda(\varphi) = 1 - C \delta(\varphi), \quad (29)$$

$$\delta(\varphi) = \frac{5}{Ma^2 \epsilon^2} \int_{\varphi_m}^{\varphi} d\varphi \frac{H(\varphi)}{\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi) \omega_0(\varphi) G(\varphi)}, \quad (30)$$

and :

$$\dot{\varphi}(\varphi) = \dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi) + C \chi(\varphi) + \mathcal{O}(C^2), \quad (31)$$

$$\chi(\varphi) = 4\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \int_{\varphi_m}^{\varphi} d\varphi \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega_0^2(\varphi) \delta(\varphi). \quad (32)$$

While (28) gives the exact expression for $\omega(\varphi)$, (31) provides an approximate yet nearly exact solution for $\dot{\varphi}(\varphi)$. Both results are interesting, even though they cannot be used algebraically. Later, we will use them to demonstrate the high efficiency of the frictionless model.

B. Exact solution of the 1st motion equation in the frictionless model

In the frictionless model, the equation of motion is the homogeneous equation associated with (26):

$$\frac{d\omega}{d\varphi} - (1 - \epsilon^4)\omega \frac{h(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)G(\varphi)} \cos\varphi \sin\varphi = 0, \quad (33)$$

If we set:

$$p = \frac{\epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2}, \quad (34)$$

$$q = \frac{\epsilon^2}{2 + \epsilon^2}, \quad (35)$$

and integrate (33) with $h(\varphi)$ as the integration variable, we obtain after calculations detailed in Appendix 6 the following expression for the egg's ascent:

$$\omega_0(\varphi) = \omega_- \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(0)}} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}}. \quad (36)$$

This implies:

$$\omega_0(0) = \omega_-, \quad (37)$$

$$\omega_1 = \omega\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \omega_- \sqrt{\frac{H(\frac{\pi}{2})}{H(0)}} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\frac{\pi}{2})} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}} = \omega_- \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \left[\frac{\epsilon^2(1 + \epsilon^2)}{2} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}}. \quad (38)$$

Note that, because a slight initial tilting of the egg is required for the ascent to occur, we actually have $\omega_- = \omega(\varphi_m)$. Since (33) implies that $[d\omega_0/d\varphi](0) = 0$, the difference between $\omega_0(0)$ and $\omega_0(\varphi_m)$ is negligible. We therefore keep $\omega_- = \omega_0(0)$ in the frictionless model. Similar results for the descent are given at the end of Appendix 6.

C. Exact solution of the 2^d motion equation in the frictionless model

Let us recall that differential equation to solve is (27):

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}^2]}{d\varphi} = 2\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega^2 - 10 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}},$$

where we now introduce (36), the expression of $\omega_0(\varphi)$. In Appendix 7, we show that, noting $d\dot{\varphi}/dt = 1/2d(\dot{\varphi}^2)/d\varphi$, a straightforward integration leads to:

$$\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi) = \sqrt{\omega_-^2 \left[\frac{G(\varphi)^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}{G(0)^\alpha} \right] - \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{10}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\sqrt{h(\varphi)} - \sqrt{h(0)} \right]}, \quad (39)$$

during the ascent. We note that:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\varphi}_0(0) &= 0 \\ \dot{\varphi}_0\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) &= \sqrt{\omega_-^2 \left[\frac{G\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}{G(0)^\alpha} \right] - \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{10}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\sqrt{h\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)} - \sqrt{h(0)} \right]}.\end{aligned}$$

We note that (39) would have nearly the form anticipated in (4) were it not for the influence of gravity. Recall that the ascent begins at $\varphi = \varphi_m$, but we retain expression (39) here for the sake of coherence. However, since $\dot{\varphi}(0) = 0$, when computing the ascent time $\int d\varphi/\dot{\varphi}$, the integration must begin at φ_C . At the end of Appendix 7, we also derive the corresponding laws for the descent.

C. The two remarkable thresholds of the egg-top

An essential feature of the phenomenon can be directly inferred from (39): two thresholds define the range of initial rotational speeds—one below which the egg-top fails to rise, and another above which it does not reach the upright position. For a given value of φ to be attained during the egg-top's ascent, and for the square root in the expression of $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ to be real, ω_- must satisfy the following condition:

$$\omega_- \geq \omega_{-min}(\varphi) = \sqrt{\frac{10}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{g}{a} G(0)^\alpha \frac{\sqrt{h(\varphi)} - \sqrt{h(0)}}{G(\varphi)^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}}. \quad (40)$$

Because $\omega_{-min}(\varphi)$ increases continuously from 0 to $\frac{\pi}{2}$, its value at $\varphi = 0$ represents the minimum value of ω_- below which the egg-top does not rise at all:

$$\omega_- \geq \omega_{-min}(0) = \lim_{\varphi \rightarrow 0} \omega_{-min}(\varphi) = \sqrt{5\epsilon \frac{g}{a}}. \quad (41)$$

Moreover, its value at $\varphi = \pi/2$ represents the minimum value of ω_- below which the egg-top fails to reach the upright position:

$$\omega_- \geq \omega_{-min}\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \sqrt{10 \frac{g}{a} \frac{(1 - \epsilon)}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{G(0)^\alpha}{G\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}}. \quad (42)$$

If, in these expressions, we replace 0 with φ_m , the numerical results are so close that, for the sake of coherence, we retain $h(0)$ and $G(0)$. For our ‘‘American dummy eggs,’’ the minimum value of ω_- above which the egg-top rises is:

$$\omega_{-min}(0) \approx 24.761 \text{ rad/s or } \approx 3.941 \text{ revolution/s,}$$

and the value above which it reaches full standing is:

$$\omega_{-min}\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \approx 26.296 \text{ rad/s or } \approx 4.185 \text{ revolution/s.}$$

Remarkably, only 0.24 revolution/s separate these two values, highlighting how efficiently rolling drives the ascent. The author of [3] has also observed the existence of these two thresholds, but experimentally.

VII TESTING OUR MODEL OF THE EGG-TOP'S MOTION

A. Predicting the egg-top's typical ascent time

Using the model to estimate the ascent time provides a good way to evaluate its predictive power. To this end, we can compute $T_{ascent} = \int_{\varphi_m}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} d\varphi/\dot{\varphi}$, using (39) for the frictionless model. However, before we proceed, we must ask ourselves whether frictional capture prolongs the ascent. To answer this, we used (29), (30), and (32) to compute numerically $\lambda(\varphi)$ and $\mu(\varphi)$, which are defined by:

$$\lambda(\varphi) = 1 - C\delta(\varphi) \text{ with } \delta(\varphi) = \frac{5}{Ma^2\epsilon^2} \int_{\varphi_m}^{\varphi} d\varphi \frac{H(\varphi)}{\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)\omega_0(\varphi)G(\varphi)},$$

$$\mu(\varphi) = \sqrt{1 + C\frac{\chi}{\dot{\varphi}_0^2}} \text{ with } \chi(\varphi) = 4\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \int_{\varphi_m}^{\varphi} d\varphi \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega_0^2(\varphi)\delta(\varphi).$$

and where:

$$\omega(\varphi) = \lambda(\varphi)\omega_0(\varphi),$$

$$\dot{\varphi}(\varphi) = \sqrt{\dot{\varphi}_0^2 + C\chi + \mathcal{O}(C^2)} = \mu(\varphi)\dot{\varphi}_0 + \mathcal{O}(C^2).$$

Choosing $\omega_- = 5$ revolutions per second, we applied our simple rotary friction model defined by $C = \frac{1}{3}\mu_d MgD$, meaning that M plays no role, as it cancels out. The dry friction coefficient for varnished wood (our experimental egg) against raw wood (our kitchen table) ranges from 0.3 to 0.6; we adopted the value $\mu_d = 0.6$. The diameter of the contact cup D was set to 2 millimeters. These calculations for various reasonable tilt angles and frictional captures cut-off angles lead to:

Tilt angle φ_m	Capture cut-off φ_c	$\lambda(\varphi_c)$	$\mu(\varphi_c)$
0.5°	5°	0.996	0.970
0.5°	10°	0.982	0.959
0.5°	15°	0.979	0.940
1°	5°	0.990	0.981
1°	10°	0.986	0.970
1°	15°	0.983	0.963
2°	5°	0.994	0.992
2°	10°	0.990	0.981
2°	15°	0.988	0.975

First, we underline that $C \approx 2.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ newton-meter explains the relatively small effects observed. Given the complexity of the integral defining $\lambda(\varphi_c)$, we

have repeated the calculations multiple times using several methods and believe the results to be reliable. This leads us to estimate that, during frictional capture, friction reduces the intrinsic internal angular speed $\omega(\varphi)$ by scarcely 1 % at $\omega_- = 5$ revolutions per second. As for the ascent-time increase factor $\mu(\varphi_c)$, taking $1/\mu(\varphi_c)$ as the maximum increase of T_{ascent} , we find that for a tilt angle of 0.5° and a frictional capture lasting over 15° —an unlikely case—the ascent duration computed using $\dot{\varphi}_0$ would increase by at most a factor of $1/0.94$, corresponding to about 6%. This suggests that, in the rotary friction model, friction has a non-negligible but small effect, confirming that the frictionless model efficiently predicts the ascent time.

Now, if we compute $T_{\text{ascent}} = \int_{\varphi_m}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} d\varphi/\dot{\varphi}_0$ for $\omega_- = 5$ revolutions per second and a tilt angle $\varphi_m = 1^\circ$, we find:

$$T_{\text{ascent},5 \text{ rev./s},1^\circ} = 0.37 \text{ s} \quad (43)$$

This value seems surprisingly small. However, in a kitchen experiment, an initial vertical angular speed of $\omega_- = 5$ revolutions per second is extremely high and well above the threshold for complete ascent (4.185 revolutions/s). Moreover, the ascent time is highly sensitive to ω_- , being roughly proportional to $1/\omega_-$. It is therefore more realistic to explore values of ω_- closer to the threshold $\omega_{-min} (\frac{\pi}{2})$. We choose:

$$\omega_- = 4.2.2\pi = 26.4 \text{ rad/s.}$$

Using this value, we sought to verify the efficiency of the frictionless model by exactly computing the ascent time in the rotary friction model for $\varphi_m=1^\circ$ and $\varphi_c=5^\circ$. To avoid the difficulties associated with computing complicated double integrals, we chose to use an exponential-polynomial interpolation of $\chi(\varphi)$. Many possibilities exist, but the function :

$$\chi_3(\varphi) = e^{-4.0575(\varphi-\varphi_m)} [3626.985064(\varphi - \varphi_m)^2 + 69202.06556(\varphi - \varphi_m)^3],$$

turned out to perform remarkably well. In fact, it is zero at $\varphi = \varphi_m$, like $\chi(\varphi_m)$, it equals $\chi(\varphi_c) = 31.05376028$ at $\varphi = \varphi_c$ and on the interval $[\varphi_m, \varphi_c]$, its curve is indistinguishable from that of $\chi(\varphi)$. Using $\chi_3(\varphi)$ in place of $\chi(\varphi)$, we computed the nearly exact ascent time in the rotary friction model and obtained:

$$T_{\text{ascent},4.2 \text{ rev./s},1^\circ,5^\circ} = 1.096 \text{ s.}, \quad (44)$$

whereas the same calculation using $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ gives, for the same tilt and capture cut-off angles, a value of $\int_{\varphi_m}^{\pi/2} d\varphi/\dot{\varphi}_0 = 1.050$ s. We see that the ascent time computed in the frictionless model is only 4.6 hundredths of a second shorter than that in the rotary friction model—an error of only 4.5 %. This calculation illustrates once again the great effectiveness of the frictionless model, which we therefore use to examine the influence of the tilt angle on the ascent time by computing $\int_{\varphi_m}^{\pi/2} d\varphi/\dot{\varphi}_0$ for several values of this angle:

Tilt angle φ_m	0.5°	1°	2°	3°	4°	5°
T_{ascent}	1.16 s.	1.05 s.	0.94 s.	0.88 s.	0.83 s.	0.80 s.

This clearly shows that, for a reasonable initial rotational speed (here, 4.2 revolutions per second), the ascent time of our egg-top—a chicken egg imitating a dummy egg—is approximately *one second*. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that a method has been developed and implemented to estimate the ascent time of an egg-top.

B. Preparation for the egg-top theory–experiment comparison

We now aim to prepare possible future experiments. We chose to do this using

Figure 4: *The evolution of $\omega_0(\varphi)$ and $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ —that is, of $\omega(\varphi)$ and $\dot{\varphi}(\varphi)$ in the frictionless version of our model—as functions of the angle φ is shown above. While $\omega_0(\varphi)$ increases from its initial value ω_- to a maximum ω_1 , $\dot{\varphi}$ rises from 0 to its maximum value $\dot{\varphi}(\pi/2)$.*

the frictionless model, since subsection VII-A shows that, at least for our experimental egg top, the initial rotary friction does not significantly affect its rise. We therefore began by plotting $\omega_0(\varphi)$, $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ for $\omega_- = 5$ revolution per second, as shown in Figure 4. The two obtained curves describe the ascent well: as the upper curve shows, $\omega_0(\varphi)$ grows steadily as the egg-top’s moment of inertia about the vertical axis diminishes; as the lower curve shows, at this relatively high initial rotational speed, the egg-top’s elevation accelerates.

This is satisfying, but not sufficient to support future comparisons with experimental curves: in fact, while φ is the same in the intrinsic frame of reference R_I and in the laboratory frame R_L , the same is not true for ω , which is difficult

to measure in the laboratory because it lies within the egg and rotates with it. Therefore, we aim to use our theoretical framework to generate curves that can be directly compared with experimental ones obtained in the laboratory. Therefore, we will describe the evolution of the “spin”, that is, $\omega_S(\varphi)$ — the component of $\vec{\omega}$ parallel to the egg’s major axis — as well as the “precession”, specifically the angular velocity $\omega_P(\varphi)$ about the vertical axis, measured in the laboratory frame of reference R_L , starting from $\omega_P(0) = \omega_-$.

Expressing the spin ω_S is straightforward, as it is simply equal to $\omega \cos \nu$. To establish the relationship between ω_P , the precession in the laboratory frame R_L and $\omega_V = \omega \sin \gamma$, the intrinsic precession in the intrinsic frame $R_I = (Gxyz)$, we need only translate (2) into the notation used here. This leads to:

$$\omega_S(\varphi) = \omega_0(\varphi) \cos \nu = \omega_- \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(0)}} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}} \frac{\sin(\varphi)}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}} \quad (45)$$

$$\omega_P(\varphi) = 2\omega_- - \omega_0(\varphi) \sin \gamma = 2\omega_- - \omega_- \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(0)}} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}} \frac{h(\varphi)}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}}, \quad (46)$$

where we have utilized $\cos \nu = \sin \varphi / \sqrt{H(\varphi)}$ and $\sin \gamma = h(\varphi) / \sqrt{H(\varphi)}$. We also want to describe ω_P , ω_S and φ as functions of time, as this could be useful for comparisons with laboratory experiments.

We decided to test our model for the same two initial rotational speeds, typical of kitchen experiments, that were already used to estimate T_{ascent} , namely:

$$\omega_- = 4.186 \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_- = 5 \text{ revolutions/s.}$$

We also had to set a value for the tilt angle and chose:

$$\varphi_m = \pi/180, \text{ that is } 1^\circ.$$

This enabled us to plot $\omega_S(\varphi)$ and $\omega_P(\varphi)$ —that is, the spin and precession as observed in R_L —alongside $\omega_0(\varphi)$ and $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$. We obtained the curves shown at the top in Figure 5. Moreover, by computing the time $t = \int_0^\varphi \frac{d\varphi}{\dot{\varphi}}$ for a sufficiently dense set of φ values, we could similarly plot ω_S , ω_P , φ and $\dot{\varphi}$ as function of t , yielding the curves shown at the bottom of Figure 5.

We observe a general structure: in the intrinsic frame of reference attached to the egg, $\omega_0(\varphi)$ increases, though only its initial and final values are measurable in practice, since the rotation axis lies inside the egg. For values of ω_- just above the threshold required to reach the vertical position, $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ increases and then decreases. However, when ω_- is well above this threshold, $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ increases monotonically. As expected, the spin $\omega_S(\varphi)$ rises from zero to a maximum, coinciding with $\omega_0(\frac{\pi}{2})$, while the precession $\omega_P(\varphi)$ decreases from an initial maximum to a minimum at $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2}$. The plots against time of $\omega_S(t)$, $\omega_P(t)$ and $\dot{\varphi}_0(t)$ show the same general behaviour.

Readers might be surprised that we have not compared our results with those from the only thorough experimental study available to date, namely [3]. In fact, we did that and discovered that the rotational speeds used by the author of [3]

Figure 5: Above: the precession and spin in the laboratory frame of reference R_L , along with $\omega_0(\varphi)$ and $\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi)$ in the intrinsic frame of reference $R_I = (Gxyz)$ of the egg, are shown for two initial angular velocities ω_- . Below: the same quantities, as well as $\varphi(t)$ and $\dot{\varphi}_0(t)$, are plotted as functions of time t , for the two same initial angular velocities ω_- .

are far higher than those achievable in a typical kitchen experiment. Nevertheless, the comparison reveals a strong similarity between the general behavior predicted by our model and the experimental results reported in [3], which we discuss in detail in Appendix 8.

VIII. A FEW WORDS OF CONCLUSION

So, where do we stand with the physics of egg-tops? Let us recall the equation $J\dot{\theta} = -Fh^2(\theta)^2$ from [3], which we discussed extensively at the beginning of this work. We now clearly know that the linear resisting force F , which opposes

the egg-top's precession in this formula, actually plays no role in the ascending motion—and likely none at all, since the spontaneous reduction of energy expenditure effectively cancels it out through rolling. Instead, we have found a "lifting torque" purely dynamic in nature and unrelated to frictional forces.

Moreover, we have identified several key features that characterize the ascent of an egg-top. First, ascent occurs as soon as the instantaneous axis of rotation deviates slightly from the vertical. We have shown that, for initial angular velocities of a few revolutions per second, typical of kitchen experiments, the egg begins to rotate intrinsically around the axis connecting its point of contact with the table to its center of mass.

For typical kitchen experiments, we obtained an almost exact mathematical description of the ascent in the rotary friction model, confirming—just as predicted at the beginning of this work—that the ascent rate is essentially proportional to the initial angular velocity. We have also shown that, at least for egg-tops resembling chicken eggs, the frictionless model is highly efficient and, in practice, sufficient. There is a threshold initial angular velocity below which the egg does not rise at all, and another below which it fails to straighten completely. The ascent duration is approximately one second in a typical kitchen experiment with egg-tops resembling chicken eggs. The egg's behaviour during ascent depends on its shape and not on its mass.

In summary, we have presented an efficient algebraic description of the ascent of a spinning egg, rigorously derived from the fundamental equations of solid-body dynamics. To our knowledge, no such description existed prior to this work, which can serve as a foundation for future experimental investigations, for example, by physics students.

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1 Modeling the rotary resistive frictional torque

We wish to establish (10), the friction torque resisting to the rotation of the contact cup centered in C , with a diameter D . In fact D is not constant and varies with the curvature at the contact point C at angle ν and with ru_{egg} , the mean rugosities of the egg’s and table surfaces. For simplicity, and to emphasize that D might vary subtly, we will simply write $D(\nu)$, recalling in this way that D varies with the bare angle ν , i.e. the elevation of the egg. We won’t attempt to give an expression for $D(\nu)$ here, as this would require experimental work that isn’t worthwhile at this stage.

Now, the contact cup is similar to a rotating disk of radius $R_\nu = D(\nu)/2$, on which any surface element $ds = dr r d\theta$ is submitted to the pressure $p = Mg/\pi R_\nu^2$. Applying now Coulomb’s friction law, we come to the conclusion, that the friction torque exerted by this surface’s element reads $dC(\nu) = \mu_d p ds r$, where μ_d is the dynamic friction coefficient. Hence, the whole friction’s torque exerted by the disk – in our case the contact cup – can be modelled as :

$$C(\nu) = \int_0^{R_\nu} dC(\nu) = \mu_d p \int_0^{R_\nu} dr r^2 d\theta = \frac{2\pi}{3} R_\nu^3 \mu_d \frac{Mg}{\pi R_\nu^2} = \frac{1}{3} \mu_d Mg D(\nu).$$

2 Establishing the geometric constraint

To prove (9), we first recall that $\gamma = \varphi + \nu$ and that:

$$r_C(\nu) = \frac{a\epsilon}{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \nu + \sin^2 \nu}}.$$

φ being fixed, we are looking for the value of ν , for which:

$$\frac{d}{d\nu} [r_C(\nu) \sin \gamma] = 0,$$

which, if we denote $dr_C(\nu)/d\nu = r'_C(\nu)$, is equivalent to:

$$\tan \gamma = -\frac{r_C(\nu)}{r'_C(\nu)}.$$

We can easily show that:

$$r'_C(\nu) = -r_C(\nu) \frac{(1 - \epsilon^2)\tan\nu}{\epsilon^2 + \tan^2\nu}.$$

Now, if we recall that:

$$\tan\gamma = \tan(\varphi + \nu) = \frac{\tan\varphi + \tan\nu}{1 - \tan\varphi\tan\nu},$$

we get the condition:

$$\frac{\tan\varphi + \tan\nu}{1 - \tan\varphi\tan\nu} = \frac{\epsilon^2 + \tan^2\nu}{(1 - \epsilon^2)\tan\nu}.$$

This translates into:

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 - \epsilon^2)\tan\varphi.\tan\nu + (1 - \epsilon^2)\tan^2\nu \\ &= \epsilon^2 + \tan^2\nu - \epsilon^2\tan\varphi.\tan\nu - \tan\varphi.\tan^3\nu. \end{aligned}$$

Removing on both sides the terms $\tan^2\nu$ and $-\epsilon^2\tan\varphi\tan\nu$ leads to:

$$\tan\varphi.\tan\nu - \epsilon^2\tan^2\nu = \epsilon^2 - \tan\varphi.\tan^3\nu,$$

that is:

$$\tan\varphi.\tan\nu(1 + \tan^2\nu) - \epsilon^2(1 + \tan^2\nu) = 0,$$

or:

$$\tan\varphi.\tan\nu = \epsilon^2,$$

which is exactly the formula (9), which we sought to demonstrate.

3 Deriving Euler's Three Equations of Motion

To establish Euler's three equations of motion, we must translate (1), which first requires recalling that:

$$\vec{\omega}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)} = [\pm\omega\cos\nu, \pm\omega\sin\nu, \pm\dot{\varphi}],$$

and that:

$$\vec{\sigma}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)} = [\pm J_{x_\varphi}\omega\cos\nu, \pm J_{y_\varphi}\omega\sin\nu, \pm J_{z_\varphi}\dot{\varphi}].$$

Hence:

$$\vec{\omega}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)} \wedge \vec{\sigma}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)} = \begin{bmatrix} \pm\omega\cos\nu \\ \pm\omega\sin\nu \\ \pm\dot{\varphi} \end{bmatrix} \wedge \begin{bmatrix} \pm J_{x_\varphi}\omega\cos\nu \\ \pm J_{y_\varphi}\omega\sin\nu \\ \pm J_{z_\varphi}\dot{\varphi} \end{bmatrix},$$

which leads to:

$$\vec{\omega}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)} \wedge \vec{\sigma}_{(Gx_\varphi y_\varphi z_\varphi)} = \begin{bmatrix} \pm(J_{z_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi})\omega \cos \nu \dot{\varphi} \\ \pm(J_{x_\varphi} - J_{z_\varphi})\omega \sin \nu \dot{\varphi} \\ (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi})\omega^2 \cos \nu \sin \nu \end{bmatrix}.$$

Now, if we recall too that:

$$\vec{M}(t) = \vec{G}\vec{C} \wedge \vec{R} + \vec{C}(\varphi) = [-C(\varphi)\cos\nu, -C(\varphi)\sin\nu, -Mg.r_C(\nu)\cos\gamma],$$

we very easily come to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}[\pm J_{x_\varphi}\omega \cos \nu] \pm (J_{z_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi})\omega \dot{\varphi} \sin \nu &= -C(\varphi)\cos\nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[\pm J_{y_\varphi}\omega \sin \nu] \pm (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{z_\varphi})\omega \dot{\varphi} \cos \nu &= -C(\varphi)\sin\nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[\pm J_{z_\varphi}\dot{\varphi}] + (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi})\omega^2 \cos \nu \sin \nu &= -Mg.r_C(\nu) \cos \gamma. \end{aligned}$$

4 Appendix: deriving the first equation of motion

We wish to establish (21). To this aim, let us first recall the two equivalent equations, which we'd like to summarize in a single one:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}[J_{x_\varphi}\omega \cos \nu] + (J_{z_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi})\omega \dot{\varphi} \sin \nu &= -C(\varphi)\cos\nu, \\ \frac{d}{dt}[J_{y_\varphi}\omega \sin \nu] + (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{z_\varphi})\omega \dot{\varphi} \cos \nu &= -C(\varphi)\sin\nu, \end{aligned}$$

We now multiply the first by $\cos\nu$ and the second by $\sin\nu$ after developing the derivatives:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos\nu \left[J_{x_\varphi} \cos\nu \omega \frac{d\omega}{dt} - J_{x_\varphi} \omega \sin\nu \dot{\nu} \right] + (J_{z_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi})\omega \cos\nu \sin\nu \dot{\varphi} \\ + \sin\nu \left[J_{y_\varphi} \sin\nu \omega \frac{d\omega}{dt} + J_{y_\varphi} \omega \cos\nu \dot{\nu} \right] + (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{z_\varphi})\omega \cos\nu \sin\nu \dot{\varphi} \\ = -C(\varphi)(\cos^2\nu + \sin^2\nu), \end{aligned}$$

which can be easily rewritten in:

$$\begin{aligned} (\cos^2\nu J_{x_\varphi} + \sin^2\nu J_{y_\varphi}) \frac{d\omega}{dt} - (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi})\omega \cos\nu \sin\nu \dot{\nu} + (J_{x_\varphi} - J_{y_\varphi})\omega \cos\nu \sin\nu \dot{\varphi} \\ = -C(\varphi), \end{aligned}$$

or:

$$J_\nu \frac{d\omega}{dt} - (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi})\omega \cos \nu \sin \nu (\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu}) = -C(\varphi),$$

ie. equation (21), which we sought to demonstrate.

5 Appendix : Transforming the equations of motion in a differential equations in φ

First, let's recall the following formulas :

$$\begin{aligned} \tan\varphi \cdot \tan\nu &= \epsilon^2, \\ J_\nu &= \cos^2 \nu J_{x_\varphi} + \sin^2 \nu J_{y_\varphi} = \frac{Ma^2}{5} j(\nu), \\ j(\nu) &= 2\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \nu + (1 + \epsilon^2) \sin^2 \nu, \\ h(\varphi) &= \epsilon^2 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi, \\ H(\varphi) &= \epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi, \\ G(\varphi) &= \epsilon^2 (1 + \epsilon^2) \cos^2 \varphi + 2 \sin^2 \varphi, \end{aligned}$$

and that we want to transform (21) and (22):

$$\begin{aligned} J_\nu \frac{d\omega}{dt} - (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi})\omega \cos\nu \sin\nu (\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu}) &= -C(\varphi), \\ J_{z_\varphi} \frac{d\dot{\varphi}}{dt} \pm (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi})\omega^2 \cos\nu \sin\nu &= -Mg r_C(\nu) \cos\gamma. \end{aligned}$$

into a differential equation in φ . We proceed by first preparing all the factors intervening from left to right in (21), which requires us to first express $\cos\nu$ and $\sin\nu$ as functions of φ . To do this, we use $\tan\nu = \epsilon^2/\tan\varphi$ in :

$$\begin{aligned} \cos\nu &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2\nu}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\epsilon^4}{\tan^2\varphi}}} = \frac{\tan\varphi}{\sqrt{\epsilon^4 + \tan^2\varphi}} = \frac{\sin\varphi}{\sqrt{\epsilon^4 \cos^2\varphi + \sin^2\varphi}} \\ \cos\nu &= \frac{\sin\varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}}, \\ \sin\nu &= \frac{\tan\nu}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2\nu}} = \frac{\frac{\epsilon^2}{\tan\varphi}}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{\epsilon^4}{\tan^2\varphi}}} = \frac{\epsilon^2}{\sqrt{\epsilon^4 + \tan^2\varphi}} = \frac{\epsilon^2 \cos\varphi}{\sqrt{\epsilon^4 \cos^2\varphi + \sin^2\varphi}} \\ \sin\nu &= \frac{\epsilon^2 \cos\varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}}. \end{aligned}$$

We now can use these results to calculate j_ν :

$$j(\nu) = 2\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \nu + (1 + \epsilon^2) \sin^2 \nu = 2\epsilon^2 \left[\frac{\sin^2 \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \right] + (1 + \epsilon^2) \left[\frac{\epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \right]$$

$$j(\nu) = \frac{\epsilon^2}{H(\varphi)} [\epsilon^2(1 + \epsilon^2) \cos^2 \varphi + 2 \sin^2 \varphi]$$

$$j(\nu) = \epsilon^2 \frac{G(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)}.$$

We now need:

$$J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi} = \frac{Ma^2}{5} [(1 + \epsilon^2) - 2\epsilon^2] = \frac{Ma^2}{5} (1 - \epsilon^2),$$

and:

$$\cos \nu \sin \nu = \epsilon^2 \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{H(\varphi)}.$$

Only $\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu}$ remains. To get its expression as a function of φ , we begin by expressing $\dot{\nu}$ as a function of φ :

$$\dot{\nu} = -\frac{\tan \nu (1 + \tan^2 \varphi)}{(1 + \tan^2 \nu) \tan \varphi} \dot{\varphi} = -\frac{\frac{\epsilon^2}{\tan \varphi} (1 + \tan^2 \varphi)}{(1 + \frac{\epsilon^4}{\tan^2 \varphi}) \tan \varphi} \dot{\varphi} = -\epsilon^2 \frac{1 + \tan^2 \varphi}{\epsilon^4 + \tan^2 \varphi} \cdot \frac{\cos^2 \varphi}{\cos^2 \varphi} \dot{\varphi}$$

$$\dot{\nu} = -\frac{\epsilon^2}{\epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi} \dot{\varphi} = -\frac{\epsilon^2}{H(\varphi)} \dot{\varphi}.$$

Hence:

$$\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu} = \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon^2}{H(\varphi)}\right) \dot{\varphi} = \frac{\epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi + \epsilon^2 (\cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi)}{H(\varphi)} \dot{\varphi}$$

$$\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu} = \frac{\epsilon^2 (1 + \epsilon^2) \cos^2 \varphi + (1 + \epsilon^2) \sin^2 \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \dot{\varphi} = (1 + \epsilon^2) \frac{\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \dot{\varphi}$$

$$\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu} = (1 + \epsilon^2) \frac{h(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)} \dot{\varphi}.$$

We can now put all pieces together:

$$\begin{bmatrix} J_\nu \\ \frac{Ma^2}{5} \frac{\epsilon^2 G(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\omega}{dt} \\ \dot{\varphi} \frac{d\omega}{d\varphi} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} (J_{y_\varphi} - J_{x_\varphi}) \\ \frac{Ma^2(1-\epsilon^2)}{5} \end{bmatrix} \omega \begin{bmatrix} \cos \nu \sin \nu \\ \frac{\epsilon^2 \cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\nu}) \\ \frac{(1+\epsilon^2)h(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)} \dot{\varphi} \end{bmatrix} = -C(\varphi),$$

and we obtain immediately:

$$\frac{d\omega}{d\varphi} - (1 - \epsilon^4) \omega \frac{h(\varphi)}{H(\varphi)G(\varphi)} \cos \varphi \sin \varphi = -\frac{5}{Ma^2 \epsilon^2} \frac{H(\varphi)C(\varphi)}{G(\varphi)\dot{\varphi}},$$

that is, equation (26), which we set out to establish.

The case of (22) is simpler: we have already given or recalled all the quantities intervening in it, except (19), ie. $J_{z_\varphi} = (1 + \epsilon^2)Ma^2/5$ and $r_C(\nu)$ given by (8):

$$r_C(\nu) = \frac{a\epsilon}{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 \cos^2 \nu + \sin^2 \nu}} = \frac{a\epsilon}{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 \frac{\sin^2 \varphi}{H(\varphi)} + \frac{\epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi}{H(\varphi)}}} = a\sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{h(\varphi)}},$$

as well as:

$$\cos \gamma = \cos \nu \cos \varphi - \sin \nu \sin \varphi = \frac{\sin \varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}} \cos \varphi - \frac{\epsilon^2 \cos \varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}} \sin \varphi = (1 - \epsilon^2) \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}}.$$

Hence:

$$\frac{Ma^2}{5}(1 + \epsilon^2)\dot{\varphi} \frac{d\dot{\varphi}}{d\varphi} = \frac{Ma^2}{5}(1 - \epsilon^2) \frac{\sin \varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}} \frac{\epsilon^2 \cos \varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}} \omega^2 - Mga \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{h(\varphi)}} (1 - \epsilon^2) \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{\sqrt{H(\varphi)}},$$

From which immediately results:

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}^2]}{d\varphi} = 2\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega^2 - 10 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{\cos \varphi \sin \varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}}$$

ie. (27).

6 Appendix : Solving the homogenous equation of motion for ω_0 for ascent

a/ For the ascent

We aim to solve the homogenous equation (33):

$$\frac{d\omega_0}{d\varphi} - (1 - \epsilon^4)\omega_0 \frac{h(\varphi)}{G(\varphi)H(\varphi)} \cos \varphi \sin \varphi = 0.$$

We first recall that:

$$\begin{aligned} h(\varphi) &= \epsilon^2 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi, \\ H(\varphi) &= \epsilon^4 \cos^2 \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi, \\ G(\varphi) &= \epsilon^2(1 + \epsilon^2)\cos^2 \varphi + 2\sin^2 \varphi = H(\varphi) + h(\varphi), \end{aligned}$$

and notice that:

$$dh(\varphi) = 2(1 - \epsilon^2)\cos \varphi \sin \varphi d\varphi.$$

This invites us to choose $h(\varphi)$ as the variable of integration. To express $H(\varphi)$ and $G(\varphi)$ as functions of h , we need $\cos^2 \varphi$ and $\sin^2 \varphi$ as functions of h :

$$\cos^2 \varphi = \frac{1 - h}{1 - \epsilon^2}, \quad \sin^2 \varphi = \frac{h - \epsilon^2}{1 - \epsilon^2},$$

which can be easily used to establish:

$$\begin{aligned} H(\varphi) &= (1 + \epsilon^2)h - \epsilon^2 = (1 + \epsilon^2)(h - p), \\ G(\varphi) &= (2 + \epsilon^2)h(\varphi) - \epsilon^2 = (2 + \epsilon^2)(h - q), \end{aligned}$$

where we recall that $p = \epsilon^2/(1 + \epsilon^2)$ and $q = \epsilon^2/(2 + \epsilon^2)$. Using all the latter results, we readily get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\omega}{\omega} &= (1 - \epsilon^4) \frac{h(\varphi)}{G(\varphi)H(\varphi)} \cos\varphi \sin\varphi d\varphi \\ &= (1 - \epsilon^4) \left[\frac{h}{(1 + \epsilon^2)(h - p)(2 + \epsilon^2)(h - q)} \right] \left[\frac{dh}{2(1 - \epsilon^2)} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2(2 + \epsilon^2)} \frac{hdh}{(h - p)(h - q)} \\ &= \frac{1}{2(2 + \epsilon^2)} \frac{1}{p - q} \left[\frac{h}{h - p} - \frac{h}{h - q} \right] dh \\ &= \frac{1}{2(2 + \epsilon^2)} \frac{1}{p - q} \left[p \frac{1}{h - p} - q \frac{1}{h - q} \right] dh. \end{aligned}$$

Now, if we note that $\epsilon^2 \leq h \leq 1$, and that $p \leq 1$ and $q \leq 1$, we can easily establish that $h - p \geq 0$ and $h - q \geq 0$, so that we can immediately integrate between 0 and φ to obtain :

$$\ln \frac{\omega}{\omega_-} = \frac{1}{2(2 + \epsilon^2)} \frac{1}{p - q} \left[p \ln \left(\frac{h - p}{\epsilon^2 - p} \right) - q \ln \left(\frac{h - q}{\epsilon^2 - q} \right) \right],$$

which, if we note that $\frac{1}{2(2 + \epsilon^2)} \frac{1}{p - q} = \frac{1}{2p}$ easily leads to:

$$\omega_0(\varphi) = \omega_- \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(0)}} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}}.$$

This is (36), that we were trying to establish.

b/ For the descent

Now, to obtain the equivalent result for the descent, we can start again from:

$$\frac{d\omega}{\omega} = \frac{1}{2p} \left[p \frac{1}{h - p} - q \frac{1}{h - q} \right] dh,$$

but this time, we integrate from ω to ω_1 and from φ to $\frac{\pi}{2}$ to maintain positive signs with the ln functions, and we obtain:

$$\omega_0(\varphi) = \omega_1 \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(\frac{\pi}{2})}} \left[\frac{G(\frac{\pi}{2})}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}},$$

which is the result we were seeking. This time, φ goes from $\frac{\pi}{2}$ to 0, which yields:

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_0\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) &= \omega_+, \\ \omega_0(0) = \omega_- &= \omega_+ \sqrt{\frac{H(0)}{H\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)}} \left[\frac{G\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{G(0)}\right]^{\frac{q}{2p}} = \omega_+ \epsilon^2 \left[\frac{2}{\epsilon^2(1+\epsilon^2)}\right]^{\frac{q}{2p}}.\end{aligned}$$

7 Appendix : Solving the 2^d equation of motion for $\dot{\varphi}_0$ for ascent and descent

a/ For the ascent

We aim to solve equation (27):

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}^2]}{d\varphi} = 2\epsilon^2 \frac{1-\epsilon^2}{1+\epsilon^2} \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega^2 - 10 \frac{1-\epsilon^2}{1+\epsilon^2} \left[\frac{g}{a}\right] \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}},$$

Introducing the expression of $\omega_0(\varphi)$:

$$\omega_0(\varphi) = \omega_- \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(0)}} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)}\right]^{\frac{q}{2p}},$$

we obtain the transformed equation:

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}_0^2]}{d\varphi} = \omega_-^2 \frac{2}{\epsilon^2} \frac{1-\epsilon^2}{1+\epsilon^2} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)}\right]^{\frac{q}{p}} \cos\varphi \sin\varphi - 10 \frac{1-\epsilon^2}{1+\epsilon^2} \left[\frac{g}{a}\right] \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}}.$$

This can be readily rewritten as:

$$d[\dot{\varphi}_0^2] = \frac{\omega_-^2}{\epsilon^2(1+\epsilon^2)} \left[\frac{G(0)}{G(\varphi)}\right]^{\frac{q}{p}} \frac{dG(\varphi)}{2+\epsilon^2} - \frac{5}{1+\epsilon^2} \frac{g}{a} \frac{dh(\varphi)}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}},$$

where:

$$p = \frac{\epsilon^2}{1+\epsilon^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad q = \frac{\epsilon^2}{2+\epsilon^2}.$$

Now, noting that:

$$\frac{d\dot{\varphi}_0}{dt} = \dot{\varphi}_0 \frac{d\dot{\varphi}_0}{d\varphi} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d[\dot{\varphi}_0^2]}{d\varphi},$$

and setting $\alpha = 1/(2+\epsilon^2)$, the straightforward integration of the latter differential equation yields:

$$\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi) = \sqrt{\omega_-^2 \left[\frac{G(\varphi)^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}{G(0)^\alpha}\right] - \left[\frac{g}{a}\right] \frac{10}{1+\epsilon^2} \left[\sqrt{h(\varphi)} - \sqrt{h(0)}\right]},$$

during this ascent, which we sought to demonstrate. We note that:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\varphi}_0(0) &= 0 \\ \dot{\varphi}_0\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) &= \sqrt{\omega_-^2 \left[\frac{G(\frac{\pi}{2})^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}{G(0)^\alpha} \right] - \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{10}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\sqrt{h(\frac{\pi}{2})} - \sqrt{h(0)} \right]}.\end{aligned}$$

b/ For the descent

This time, the equation to solve is:

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}^2]}{d\varphi} = -2\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{H(\varphi)} \omega^2 - 10 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}},$$

where we, this time, introduce:

$$\omega_0(\varphi) = \omega_1 \sqrt{\frac{H(\varphi)}{H(\frac{\pi}{2})} \left[\frac{G(\frac{\pi}{2})}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{2p}}}.$$

Thus by following the same steps as in the case of the ascent, we readily obtain:

$$\frac{d[\dot{\varphi}_0^2]}{d\varphi} = -\omega_1^2 2\epsilon^2 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{G(\frac{\pi}{2})}{G(\varphi)} \right]^{\frac{q}{p}} \cos\varphi \sin\varphi - \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] 10 \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \frac{\cos\varphi \sin\varphi}{\sqrt{h(\varphi)}}. \quad (47)$$

We integrate again between φ and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and follow the same steps as in the previous case to obtain :

$$\dot{\varphi}_0(\varphi) = -\sqrt{\omega_1^2 \frac{2\epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{G(\varphi)^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}{G(\frac{\pi}{2})^\alpha} \right] + \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{10}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\sqrt{h(\varphi)} - \sqrt{h(0)} \right]}.$$

We note that, when φ goes from $\frac{\pi}{2}$ to 0, we have:

$$\dot{\varphi}_0\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = -\sqrt{\omega_1^2 \frac{2\epsilon^2}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\frac{G(\frac{\pi}{2})^\alpha - G(0)^\alpha}{G(\frac{\pi}{2})^\alpha} \right] + \left[\frac{g}{a} \right] \frac{10}{1 + \epsilon^2} \left[\sqrt{h(\frac{\pi}{2})} - \sqrt{h(0)} \right]},$$

$$\dot{\varphi}_0(0) = 0.$$

8 Appendix : Discussing the experimental results presented in [3]

To compare our results with the experimental data presented in [3] by Rod Cross of the University of Sydney, we simply substituted into our equations the parameters from one of his experiments. The latter involved an aluminum ellipsoid "S1", with a long axis of $a = 29.95$ millimeters, a short axis of $b = 19.98$ millimeters and a mass of 132 grams, launched with a vertical rotational speed ω_- of 90 rad/s. The curves for precession ω_P , spin ω_S and angle φ as functions

Figure 6: *On the left, the curves show the precession ω_P , the spin ω_S , the intrinsic rotation speed ω , and the elevation speed $\dot{\varphi}$ as functions of φ for one of the aluminum experimental egg S1 used in study [3], launched with an initial rotation speed of 14.3 revolutions per second. In the center, the precession, spin, elevation speed, and angle φ are shown as functions of time. On the right, for comparison, the curves for precession (noted Ω), spin (noted ω), and angle (noted $\theta = \pi/2 - \varphi$) from [3] (R. Cross, *Eur. J. Phys.*, 2018.) are displayed.*

of either φ or time t , along with Rod Cross's results, are shown in Figure 6. Comparing the behaviour of ω_P and ω_S across the three graphs, we take some comfort in the fact that their qualitative trends are similar, as this confirms that the egg's ascent is primarily driven by its rotational motion. However, the values reached by the precession and by the spin in the laboratory frame differ between our theoretical calculations and the experimental results. What's more, the egg doesn't rise completely, and the time scales don't match: the experimental time scale is ten times longer than the theoretical one. As a result, the theoretical and experimental behaviours do not align quantitatively.

There must be a systemic reason for this difference, because the experimental curve shows some truly surprising characteristics. First, the initial angular speed of 90 radians per second (14.3 revolutions per second) is enormous: in the case of S1, the minimal initial angular speed required for the egg to fully straighten while rolling, as described in our model, is $\omega_{-min}(\frac{\pi}{2}) = 35.75$ rad/s (or 5.69 revolutions per second). Yet, although ω_- is more than 2.5 times greater than $\omega_{-min}(\frac{\pi}{2})$, the egg doesn't straighten completely, reaching only $\varphi = 70^\circ$ ($\theta = 20^\circ$). Another surprising aspect is the time scale, which we know should be on the order of $1/\omega_-$; in fact, we estimated T_{ascent} as described in section VII-A and found it to be 0.06 s, while the experimental curve indicates a value of approximately 0.8 s. This suggests that some unaccounted-for phenomenon dissipates part of the initial kinetic energy and consumes time.

To test this hypothesis, we can compare the egg's energy at the beginning of its ascent with its energy when it reaches an angle of 70° . The initial energy imparted to the egg is:

$$\frac{1}{2} J_{y_\varphi} 90^2 = 0,138 \text{ joule,}$$

From the experimental graph, we observe that when the egg reaches its maximum elevation angle of 70 degrees, it precesses at approximately 50 rad/s and spins at around 55 rad/s. Therefore, the egg's energy at this maximum elevation angle is approximately:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left[\cos^2\left(\frac{20\pi}{180}\right) J_{x\varphi} + \sin^2\left(\frac{20\pi}{180}\right) J_{y\varphi} \right] 50^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_{x\varphi} 55^2 + Mg a \cos\left(\frac{20\pi}{180}\right) = 0.096 \text{ joule,}$$

where we have used (16) to obtain J_{ν} , and have included the gravitational energy gained by the egg. This means that the experimental egg, while rising only to 70°, has lost more than 30 % of its energy.

Could this be explained by the fact that friction has not been taken into account during the initial frictional capture? No, because such an effect would be insufficient to account for a 30 % loss of energy, even if we assume that, at such a high initial rotational speed, rotary friction persists up to an angle of 70°. To demonstrate this, we calculated $\lambda(70\pi/180)$ using a dynamic dry friction coefficient for aluminum on varnished wood of $\mu_d = 0.3$, based on our review of the literature, and a contact cup diameter of 1 millimeter. We obtained $\lambda(70\pi/180) = 0.999$, leading to a spin value of $\omega_S(70\pi/180) = 139.1$ rad/s—only slightly below the instantaneous rotation speed in the intrinsic frame, $\omega(70\pi/180) = 141.1$ rad/s. Rotary friction during the frictional capture therefore accounts for neither the values reached by $\omega_S(\varphi)$ and $\omega_P(\varphi)$ at 70°, nor for the observed loss of energy.

Figure 7: On the left, the curves show the spin $\omega_S(\varphi)$ and precession $\omega_P(\varphi)$ for the initial angular speed $\omega_- = 33,56 \text{ rad/s}$, which drives the ascent only up to 70°. On the right, the same curves are shown with a phenomenological modification introduced to represent the effect of a presumed initial phase of rotation about the vertical axis without immediate ascent.

An alternative scenario taking the initial rotary friction into account in a different way may better explain the difference between theory and experiment when S1 is launched at 90 rad/s. As we wrote in Section III-B, “a perfectly ellipsoidal egg, placed perfectly horizontally on a perfectly flat plane, will theoretically never rise.” In practice, a high initial angular velocity merely serves to stabilize

the egg's rotation around its vertical axis for a time, during which its angular velocity gradually decreases as it is dissipated, until it reaches the range where frictional capture can more readily occur.

Therefore, we can only suppose that, in the experiment under discussion, the egg's stabilized angular velocity decreased to a value close to that required to trigger a frictional capture, followed by an ascent up to 70° . Using our equations, we have numerically determined that the intermediate angular velocity necessary to achieve an ascent to 70° , once the frictional capture inducing significant rolling has occurred, is approximately 35.56 rad/s. This result leads to the curves shown in Figure 7 on the left, and we are pleased to find that our equations yield a final spin of 55 rad/s at 70° , which is very close to the value observed on the experimental graph. The calculation of T_{ascent} also yields a very satisfactory result: its value of 0.54 s places the time scale in the correct order of magnitude, likely close to the 0.8 s that would be observed if friction were taken into account.

The shape of the precession is also encouraging. Our model cannot capture the long initial rotary sliding that, in Rod Cross's experiment, precedes according to us frictional capture, followed by rolling possibly accompanied at such high speed by residual rotary sliding during ascent, which likely occurs at sufficiently low rotational speeds. In our opinion, this explains why the magnitude of the precession is not accurate. Therefore, it is reasonable to phenomenologically represent a more realistic evolution of precession in the laboratory frame by adding to $\omega_P(\varphi)$ a term that allows the theoretical curve of our model to reach the experimental value of 50 rad/s observed on the experimental curve. This term, 33.6 rad/s, accounts for both the initial reduction in angular speed—albeit partially—and the braking effect of the residual rotary slip. This adjustment is illustrated on the right of Figure 7.

From these considerations, we conclude that, because they primarily capture the dynamics, our equations possess sufficient predictive power to approximately reproduce most aspects of the experimental curves for the solid ellipsoid S1, launched with the enormous initial angular velocity of 90 rad/s. However, we must stress that this situation does not correspond to the kitchen experiments for which our model was developed, where initial rotational speeds of only a few revolutions per second allow nearly immediate frictional capture and rolling.